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Outputs: Insights into Farm
Multiple-Output Flexibility**

Discussion paper

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Joint Production of Environmental and Market Outputs: Insights into Farm Multiple-Output Flexibility

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Abstract

The study examines the relationship between environmental subsidies and farmers' motivations in selected European Union (EU) countries. Building on the hypothesis that agri-environmental commitments generally require substantial changes in production technology, the study analyses economies of scale, economies of scope, and output cost complementarities across four EU countries. These concepts are examined using stochastic Input Distance Function (IDF) models estimated through the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM), based on data from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) covering the period 2008–2021. The results indicate that diseconomies of scope prevail across all analysed countries, suggesting that the joint production of environmental and market outputs does not generate cost savings. Moreover, larger farms exhibit more pronounced diseconomies of scope and, consequently, weaker incentives to adjust their production structures towards environmental provision. In contrast, smaller farms are characterised by lower flexibility and, therefore, a reduced capacity to adapt their production structures to changing conditions.

Key words: agriculture, environmental output, output flexibility, duality, input distance function.

JEL classifications: *D24, O12, P27.*

Introduction

Growing environmental concerns have increased societal pressure to transition agriculture from conventional practices towards more environmentally sustainable farming systems that deliver positive environmental outcomes. In this context, farm diversification, particularly through the utilisation of underexploited resources and the adoption of sustainable production practices, has become a key priority within environmental policy frameworks (Manevska-Tasevska et al., 2015). In the European Union (EU), the provision of environmental outputs is supported through voluntary Agri-Environmental-Climatic Schemes (AECs). Originating in the 1980s, these policy instruments were designed to improve environmental and natural conditions in agricultural areas by inducing changes in farmers' environmental behaviour (Cullen et al., 2021; Pavlis et al., 2016).

Since their introduction, a substantial body of research has examined the factors influencing participation in AECs. This literature has predominantly focused on socio-economic and structural characteristics, as well as the role of psychological factors and social capital (Bojnec and Fertő, 2025; Fertő and Bojnec, 2025; Diop et al., 2024; Podruzsik and Fertő, 2024; Cullen et al., 2021; Wąs et al., 2021; Bostian et al., 2020; Dessart et al., 2019; Todorova, 2019; Defrancesco et al., 2018; Pavlis et al., 2016; Gailhard and Bojnec, 2015). Comprehensive reviews by Canessa et al. (2024), Schaub et al. (2023), Tey et al. (2017), and Lastra-Bravo et al. (2015) highlight several consistent findings. Farms located in upland and mountainous regions, as well as in Less Favoured Areas (LFAs), where land productivity is generally lower, exhibit higher participation rates in AECs, as scheme payments are often perceived as an additional income source that compensates for natural constraints and production risks.

Younger farmers – particularly those with stronger pro-environmental attitudes – as well as farmers with specialised agricultural training and access to advisory services, show a greater inclination to adopt environmentally friendly practices, reflecting increased openness to innovation, stronger learning capacity, and enhanced managerial flexibility. Information and experience also play a crucial role in adoption decisions: farmers who are better informed about agri-environmental practices, and those who possess either direct experience or indirect knowledge through neighbouring farmers, are more likely to participate in AECs (Schaub et al., 2023; Tey et al., 2017; Lastra-Bravo et al., 2015). Moreover, information obtained from peers appears to have a stronger influence on adoption behaviour than information disseminated by scientists (Villamayor-Tomas et al., 2019).

Evidence regarding the role of farm size remains mixed. Larger farms generally face fewer barriers to participation in AECs, benefiting from lower opportunity costs due to greater flexibility in labour and machinery allocation, as well as a higher likelihood of managing lower-productivity land within their total utilised agricultural area (Schaub et al., 2023). Consequently, participation rates tend to be higher among larger farms. Complementing this perspective, Ducos et al. (2009) highlight the role of fixed compliance and transaction costs, demonstrating their disproportionate impact as barriers to participation for smaller farms.

However, comparatively little is known about farmers' production-related motivations for providing environmental outputs, even though participation in AECs typically entails substantial changes in farm production technologies, production costs, efficiency, and productivity. The provision of environmental outputs is therefore embedded within farm-level production decisions, reflecting technical interdependencies, the joint use of fixed non-allocable inputs, and competition for allocable inputs (Brunstad et al., 2005; Gullstrand et al., 2014). Where physical synergies exist, the joint

production of market and environmental outputs may give rise to economies of scope and generate benefits for farms (Panzar and Willig, 1981).

Although the empirical literature remains limited, several contributions stand out. Among the pioneering studies, Peerlings and Polman (2004) analysed the joint production of milk and environmental outputs, including wildlife and landscape services, by estimating the shadow prices of environmental services corresponding to their marginal costs of provision. Their findings indicate the presence of economies of scope, reflecting efficiency gains from joint production, albeit only for a subset of farms. Gullstrand et al. (2014) further examined how the marginal costs of market outputs, including crops, milk, and beef, derived from a cost function, respond to biodiversity provision. They identify complementarity with crop production but competitive relationships with milk and beef production. Using a short-run cost function framework, Lambini et al. (2018) similarly report economies of scope in the joint provision of forest ecosystem services. By contrast, Ruijs et al. (2017), employing a multiple-output frontier approach, find evidence of diseconomies of scope between agricultural revenues and ecosystem services.

Beyond scope effects, the literature has also examined scale and productivity implications. Tamini et al. (2012) show that farms adopting agri-environmental practices, such as reduced herbicide use, may experience modest increases in economies of scale, possibly because these practices release capital and labour that can subsequently be reallocated to expand production. Omer et al. (2007) demonstrate that biodiversity, through the provision of ecological services, can enhance agricultural output and induce a continual outward shift of the production frontier, conditional on relevant labour and capital inputs. Similarly, Castaldo et al. (2025) report productivity gains associated with participation in AECSS, potentially driven by land-augmenting technical change. Taken together, these findings suggest that the provision of environmental outputs may reflect optimising behaviour by farmers. However, Areal et al. (2012) and Bostian et al. (2020) document efficiency and productivity losses linked to the adoption of agri-environmental practices.

The mixed empirical evidence may reflect farm heterogeneity, differences in production orientation, and variation in the types of environmental outputs considered (Olof and Nilsson, 2009; Ruijs et al., 2017; Wimmer and Sauer, 2020; Diop et al., 2024). The lack of consistent findings complicates policy design, as public support may be allocated to farms that would provide environmental outputs even in the absence of intervention, thereby generating windfall effects (Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013). Against this background, the present study seeks to strengthen the evidence base for policy design by analysing farm flexibility and its components, with particular emphasis on crop farms in four European countries.

The objective of this study is to better understand the determinants of structural adjustment in agriculture in the context of agri-environmental commitments. Hypothesising that such commitments generally require substantial changes in production technology and are therefore expected to influence economies of scope and scale, as well as farm practices addressing resource scarcity, the study employs the concept of multiple-output flexibility to investigate structural adjustment processes associated with agri-environmental commitments. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) estimate production technology with both environmental and marketed outputs; (ii) measure farm multiple-output flexibility and its components; and (iii) evaluate farmers' incentives for the joint production of environmental and market outputs, with particular attention to differences between small and large farms.

The contribution of this study is fourfold. First, it offers novel insights into the motivations underlying the provision of environmental outputs by drawing on the concept of flexibility, empirically evaluated using the system Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) estimator. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first application of the flexibility concept to examine motivations for sustainable farming practices. Earlier studies analysed flexibility as a source of farm-level competitiveness without incorporating environmental outputs, including Renner et al. (2014) for Poland and Bokusheva and Čechura (2017) for Germany, England, the Czech Republic, Poland, and Hungary. Furthermore, by integrating economies of scale, economies of scope, and environmental output provision within a unified analytical framework, this study bridges strands of the literature that have largely been examined in isolation.

Second, it provides a comprehensive empirical assessment by employing subsidies targeted at climate- and environmentally beneficial practices as proxies for environmental outputs. Third, the study contributes to the assessment of the cost-effectiveness of subsidies by evaluating the presence of windfall effects while explicitly accounting for farm heterogeneity. Fourth, in contrast to previous studies focusing on single-country evidence, this analysis covers four EU Member States, Poland, the Czech Republic, Germany, and France, thereby enabling the exploration of cross-country differences.

The structure of the study is as follows. The following sections outline the theoretical framework, present the empirical strategy, and describe the data used in the analysis. The subsequent section reports the estimation results, compares the estimated production technology and flexibility, and discusses the findings. The final sections offer policy implications and concluding remarks.

Theoretical Framework

Agricultural producers operate under evolving economic and policy conditions. Increasing pressures to enhance the environmental sustainability of agricultural production, coupled with growing demand for high-quality food products, compel producers to adjust both their production structures and the technologies they employ. Their ability to respond to these changing conditions critically affects their competitiveness and long-term economic viability. Because such adjustments are often associated with increases in average production costs, competitiveness and viability may depend on a farm's ability to adjust both its overall output level and the composition of its production mix while maintaining its average cost level. This capacity is referred to as multiple-output flexibility (Stigler, 1939; Renner et al., 2014; Renner et al., 2015).

The agricultural production process is naturally characterised by the transformation of multiple inputs into multiple outputs. Let $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_K)$ denote a non-negative vector of K inputs and $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_M)$ a vector of M outputs. The transformation process can then be represented as follows:

$$L(\mathbf{y}) = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}_+^K : \mathbf{y} \in R_+^M \text{ is produced by } \mathbf{x}\}, \quad (1)$$

where $L(\mathbf{y})$ is the input requirement set that is assumed to be a closed and non-empty set satisfying the standard neoclassical assumption of convexity (Chambers, 1988).

Under the behavioural assumption that agricultural producers choose an input vector that minimises the cost of producing a given output vector, and that they operate in perfectly competitive input markets, the transformation process can be analysed using a cost function representation, hereafter denoted as C :

$$C(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{y}) = \min_{\mathbf{x}} \{\mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{x} : \mathbf{x} \in L(\mathbf{y})\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_K)$ is a price vector ($\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}_+^K$). According to Shephard (1970), the cost function has the following properties: (i) is non-negative and non-decreasing in \mathbf{p} ; (ii) homogenous of degree one in \mathbf{p} ; (iii) concave and continuous in \mathbf{p} ; and (iv) non-decreasing in \mathbf{y} .

Flexibility finds its expression in the curvature of the average cost curve. Stigler (1939) defined flexibility for the production with one output as a second derivatives of the average costs:

$$Flex = \frac{\partial^2(C/y)}{\partial y^2} = \frac{1}{y^3} [y^2 C_{yy} - 2(yC_y - C)], \quad (3)$$

where C_{yy} is the second order and C_y the first order derivatives of the cost function C with respect to the output y . The higher the curvature of the average cost curve, the lower the degree of flexibility, defined as the farm's ability to respond to changing conditions.

Crémieux et al. (2005) extended this measure of flexibility to multiple-output firms:

$$Flex = \mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{C}_{yy} \mathbf{y} + 2C(1 - \mathbf{1}_M^T \mathbf{E}_y), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{C}_{yy} represents the (MxM) Hessian matrix of the cost function with respect to M outputs, $\mathbf{1}_M$ is the (Mx1) unit vector, and \mathbf{E}_y is the (Mx1) vector of partial cost elasticities with respect to M outputs: $\varepsilon_{y_m}^C = \frac{\partial C}{\partial y_m} \frac{y_m}{C}$.

To provide deeper insights, Renner et al. (2014) propose the decomposition of this multiple-output flexibility into three components by splitting the Hessian matrix: $\mathbf{C}_{yy} = \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{Diag} + \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{-Diag}$:

$$Flex = \mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{Diag} \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{-Diag} \mathbf{y} + 2C(1 - \mathbf{1}_M^T \mathbf{E}_y), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{Diag} \mathbf{y}$ is the convexity effect building on the elements on principal diagonal, $\mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{C}_{yy}^{-Diag} \mathbf{y}$ is the scope effect using off-diagonal elements and $2C(1 - \mathbf{1}_M^T \mathbf{E}_y)$ is the scale effect.

The scope effect, also referred to as the complementarity effect, captures the presence of economies of scope, a concept describing cost advantages associated with production diversification. Economies of scope arise when it is less costly to produce multiple outputs jointly within a single production process than to produce them separately. Conversely, diseconomies of scope occur when joint production leads to higher total costs (Hajargasht et al., 2008). As noted by Baumol et al. (1982), these cost interactions reflect the degree to which production activities are technologically or economically interrelated. Cost savings typically emerge from the sharing or joint utilisation of input resources across diversified production technologies (Renner et al., 2014).

The scale effect refers to economies or diseconomies of scale that arise when a small proportional increase in the levels of all inputs leads to a more than proportional or less than proportional increase in the levels of all outputs (Panzar and Willig, 1977). Within the cost function framework, economies of scale arise when costs increase at a slower rate than output. Conversely, diseconomies of scale occur when costs increase at a faster rate than output (Baumol et al., 1982). Cost savings resulting from economies of scale often originate from the intensification and specialisation of the production process. De Roest et al. (2017) further argue that economies of scale are closely linked to capital-intensive technological development. The adoption of technological innovations enhances productivity and reduces costs per unit of output.

The convexity effect refers to the curvature of the marginal cost function arising from resource scarcity (Renner et al., 2014). Lower values of the convexity term are associated with greater flexibility, indicating that existing technologies are able, to some extent, to compensate for or alleviate resource

constraints. The presence of a convexity effect therefore suggests that technological conditions can mitigate the impact of resource scarcity, adjusting in the scale of operations less costly (Bokusheva and Čechura, 2017).

However, estimating the cost function requires input price data at the farm level, which are often difficult to obtain. To address this limitation, Hajargasht et al. (2008), in their analysis of economies of scope, propose exploiting the duality between the cost function and the input distance function (IDF). This duality implies that the cost function can be derived from the IDF, and vice versa. Färe and Primont (1995, p. 47) formally define this dual relationship as follows:

$$C(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{y}) = \min_{\mathbf{x}} \{\mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{x} : D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) \geq 1\} \quad (6)$$

if and only if

$$D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) = \inf_{\mathbf{p}} \{\mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{x} : C(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{p}) \geq 1\},$$

where $D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x})$ denotes the IDF, which is assumed to exhibit the following properties: it is non-decreasing, positively linearly homogeneous, concave in inputs, and non-increasing and convex in outputs (Färe and Primont, 1995).

According to Hajargasht et al. (2008), economies of scope can be calculated using the derivatives of the IDF:

$$C_{yy} = C \{ \mathbf{D}_y \mathbf{D}_y^T - \mathbf{D}_{yy} + \mathbf{D}_{yx} (\mathbf{D}_{xx} + \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{D}_x^T)^{-1} \mathbf{D}_{xy} \}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{D}_y and \mathbf{D}_x are vectors of first derivatives of the IDF with respect to M outputs and K inputs, respectively; \mathbf{D}_{yy} , \mathbf{D}_{xx} , and \mathbf{D}_{xy} denote matrices of second-order derivatives of the IDF with respect to outputs and inputs, respectively.

Equation (7) can be further adjusted using the relationship between the cost function and the IDF, as derived by Renner et al. (2014) through the application of the Lagrange method to the cost minimisation problem:

$$C = (\mathbf{1}_K^T \mathbf{D}_x)^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{1}_K$ is the $(K \times 1)$ unit vector, \mathbf{D}_x is a $(K \times 1)$ vector of the first derivatives of the input distance function with respect to K inputs.

This allows flexibility in Eq. (5) to be formulated on the basis of the IDF as follows (Renner et al. (2014):

$$Flex = (\mathbf{1}_N^T \mathbf{D}_x)^{-1} \mathbf{y}^T [\mathbf{D}_y \mathbf{D}_y^T - \mathbf{D}_{yy} + \mathbf{D}_{yx} (\mathbf{D}_{xx} + \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{D}_x^T)^{-1} \mathbf{D}_{xy}] \mathbf{y} + 2(\mathbf{1}_N^T \mathbf{D}_x)^{-1} (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{y}^T \mathbf{D}_y \mathbf{D}^{-1}). \quad (9)$$

Empirical strategy

The multiple-output, multiple-input transformation process of a farm is assumed to be well approximated by a translog IDF with four outputs, three market outputs and one environmental output, and four inputs, land, labour, capital, and materials. The translog functional form is used because of its flexibility in representing convex output sets and its ability to accommodate homogeneity restrictions (Coelli and Perelman, 1996). The translog IDF is defined as follows:

$$\ln D_{it}^I = \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k \ln x_{k,it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=1}^K \beta_{kl} \ln x_{k,it} \ln x_{l,it} + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{km} \ln x_{k,it} \ln y_{m,it} \quad (10)$$

where subscripts l and t , with $i = 1, \dots, I$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$, refer to the i -th farm and time t , respectively, and α , β , and γ are vectors of parameters to be estimated.

As the IDF is assumed to be homogenous of degree one in inputs, the parameters in Eq. (10) must satisfy the following restrictions: $\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k = 1$, $\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{kl} = 0$, $\sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_{km} = 0$. Moreover, the symmetry restrictions imply: $\alpha_{mn} = \alpha_{nm}$ and $\beta_{kl} = \beta_{lk}$.

Following Lovell et al. (1994), homogeneity is imposed by normalising all the inputs by one input (x_1) resulting in:

$$\ln D_{it}^I - \ln x_{1,it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \sum_{k=2}^K \beta_k \ln x_{k,it}^* + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=2}^K \sum_{l=2}^K \beta_{kl} \ln x_{k,it}^* \ln x_{l,it}^* + \sum_{k=2}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{km} \ln x_{k,it}^* \ln y_{m,it} \quad (11)$$

where $x_{k,it}^* = \frac{x_{k,it}}{x_{1,it}}$.

Introducing farm heterogeneity μ_i and a stochastic error term $v_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$, and associating $\ln D_{it}^I$ with inefficiency, i.e., $\ln D_{it}^I = u_{it} + \eta_i$, where $u_{it} \sim N^+(0, \sigma_u^2)$ represents transient inefficiency and $\eta_i \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$ is persistent inefficiency, the IDF to be estimated is specified as follows (Kumbhakar and Lovell, 2000):

$$-\ln x_{1,it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \sum_{k=2}^K \beta_k \ln x_{k,it}^* + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=2}^K \sum_{l=2}^K \beta_{kl} \ln x_{k,it}^* \ln x_{l,it}^* + \sum_{k=2}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{km} \ln x_{k,it}^* \ln y_{m,it} + \mu_i + v_{it} - u_{it} - \eta_i \quad (12)$$

To estimate the parameters of the IDF consistently, this study follows the procedure of Bokusheva and Čechura (2017) and employs the system Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) estimator (Arellano and Bover, 1995; Blundell and Bond, 1998), which controls for the potential endogeneity of netputs. The system GMM combines two equations: the original specification in levels and a transformed specification in first differences. It also employs two sets of instruments, lagged levels as instruments for the differenced equation and lagged differences as instruments for the level equation. The validity of the instrument set is assessed using the Hansen J test (Hansen, 1982), which examines their joint exogeneity. In addition, the Arellano and Bond (1991) test is applied to detect autocorrelation in the idiosyncratic disturbance term, as the presence of serial correlation may invalidate certain lagged instruments.

Furthermore, to explain variation in economies of scope and complementarity between market and environmental outputs, a panel regression model is specified following the approach of Bokusheva and Čechura (2017) and incorporating factors commonly used in studies examining the determinants of farmers' participation in AECSs based on FADN data (e.g. Bojnec and Fertó, 2025; Wąs et al., 2021). To account for unobserved heterogeneity in the panel data, the analysis initially employs a correlated random effects specification following Mundlak (1978). If the Mundlak devices, defined as the group means of time-varying regressors, are jointly statistically insignificant at the 10 percent significance level, the preferred specification is chosen between standard random effects and fixed effects models based on the Hausman test results. Potential endogeneity of the explanatory variables is addressed using a control function approach. Specifically, two period and three period lags of the potentially endogenous regressors, together with year dummies, are used as instruments in the first stage regression. All estimations are conducted in Stata 18.

Data

The empirical analysis employs an unbalanced panel dataset drawn from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database provided by the European Commission. This database is the only official source of harmonised microeconomic data, both physical and financial, on commercial farms in the European Union (EU). It contains information on approximately 80,000 agricultural holdings across the EU. The dataset is representative across three dimensions: region, economic size, and type of farming.

This study focuses on four EU Member States located in the temperate climate zone with broadly comparable agricultural conditions: Poland, the Czech Republic, Germany, and France. Within the FADN database, these countries are represented by 112,601 observations from 21,808 cereal, field crop, and mixed crop farms over the period 2008 to 2021. More specifically, the analysis draws on the following FADN types of farming: TF 15, specialist cereals, oilseeds, and protein crops; TF 16, specialist other field crops; and TF 60, mixed crops. The country level distribution is as follows: 52,452 observations from 11,150 farms in Poland; 6,287 observations from 1,195 farms in Czechia; 29,548 observations from 5,461 farms in Germany; and 24,314 observations from 4,002 farms in France.

However, because not all farms reported complete information on inputs and outputs, and to enable the use of the GMM estimator with a sufficient number of lagged instruments, the dataset is restricted to farms with non-missing observations and at least five consecutive years of data. The final sample, therefore, comprises 43,756 observations from 5,265 farms. Table 1 presents the sample structure by country.

Table 1 Structure of the dataset

Country	Number of observations	Number of farms
Poland	10,566	1,405
Czechia	4,116	461
Germany	16,564	1,988
France	12,510	1,411

Source: FADN EU

The transformation process is described by four inputs, materials, land, labour, and capital, and four outputs, cereals output, other crop output, other farm output, and environmental output. Detailed variable definitions are provided in Table 2, and descriptive statistics are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix.

The use of subsidies targeted at climate and environmentally beneficial practices as a proxy for environmental outputs reflects the lack of FADN data on the provision of environmental goods. Alternative proxies have nevertheless been employed in the literature. Areal et al. (2012), for instance, use the share of permanent grassland relative to rough grazing within total utilised agricultural area. However, a subsidy-based proxy may be considered more comprehensive and, insofar as payments are properly calibrated to reflect the societal valuation of public goods, provides a relevant approximation of environmental output.

Explanatory variables capturing variation in economies of scope, complementarity, and additional characteristics are presented in Table A2 in the Appendix, together with their descriptive statistics. In addition, the following variables are used as instruments. For Poland, the instrument set includes the output price index, the total input price index, the share of cereals in arable land, the share of energy crop area, dummy variables for altitude between 300 and 600 metres above sea level, a dummy variable for altitude above 600 metres above sea level, a dummy for Less Favoured Areas (LFA), and the share of net investment in fixed assets. For Czechia, the instruments comprise output price indices,

the share of rented land, fertiliser and pesticide intensity, seed expenditures per hectare, and a dummy variable for long term loans. For Germany, the instrument set consists of output price indices, input price indices, wages per annual working unit, the area shares of permanent crops and energy crops, and dummy variables for LFA and field crop farming. Finally, for France, the instruments include output price indices, the total input price index, the share of cereals in arable land, net investment per hectare of utilised agricultural area, and dummy variables for altitude between 300 and 600 metres above sea level and for LFA.

Table 2 Description of IDF variables

Variable	Description (FADN code)	Price indices (2010=100)
Cereals	Cereals output (SE140)	Cereals (SE140)
Other crop output	Total crop output except cereals (SE135-SE140)	Crop output
Other farm output	Livestock output and other farm output (SE206+SE256)	Animals (SE206-SE216), Milk (SE216) agricultural goods (SE256)
Environmental output	Payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment, agri-environment-climate and animal welfare payments, organic farming subsidy, and Natura 2000 payments	Agricultural goods
Materials	Total specific costs and total farming overheads (SE275-SE350)	Goods and services currently consumed in agriculture
Land	Utilised agricultural area (SE025)	
Labour	Total labour input in annual working unit (AWU, SE010)	
Capital	Depreciation of fixed assets and contract work (SE360+SE350)	Goods and services contributing to agricultural investment

Source: Own processing

All monetary variables are deflated using price indices with 2010 as the base year obtained from Eurostat (2025). The applied indices are reported in Table 2. Further data transformation requires the specification of the transformation function within the IDF framework using a translog functional form. Accordingly, the IDF variables are logarithmically transformed and normalised by their sample means. This procedure allows the first-order IDF parameters to be interpreted as output elasticities and input cost shares evaluated at the sample mean.

Results and discussion

Production technology

The estimated IDF parameters for individual countries are presented in Table A3 in the Appendix. The table first reports the first-order parameters, followed by the second-order parameters, and concludes with the results of the F tests, the AR(2) test, and Hansen's J test. Across all countries, most first-order parameters are statistically significant at the 1 percent level. An exception is Germany, where the first-order capital parameter is statistically significant only at the 10 percent level. The statistical significance of a substantial share of the second-order parameters, together with the F test results, supports the use of the flexible translog specification to adequately capture the transformation process with environmental output. Furthermore, the AR(2) test and Hansen's J test statistics confirm the validity of the GMM estimates.

Beyond the statistical properties discussed above, the estimated IDF must also satisfy theoretical regularity conditions to ensure a proper representation of the underlying transformation process. The theoretical consistency of the IDF requires that the estimated parameters satisfy the assumptions of

monotonicity and quasi-concavity. With respect to monotonicity, the results indicate that the estimated IDFs are non-increasing in outputs and non-decreasing in inputs when evaluated at the corresponding sample means. Quasi-concavity requires the Hessian matrix of second-order derivatives of the IDF with respect to inputs to be negative semidefinite (Diewert and Wales, 1987). This condition is also satisfied at the sample means for each input variable, confirming that the estimated IDFs meet the required theoretical properties.

To characterise the transformation process with environmental output, Table 3 reports the IDF elasticities with respect to individual outputs and inputs, together with the estimated economies of scale, calculated as arithmetic means across the country samples. Following Singbo and Larue (2016), IDF elasticities with respect to outputs indicate the relative importance of each output, as they represent the shadow shares of outputs in total farm production. Since production in all countries exhibits economies of scale, Table 3 also reports output shadow shares adjusted to constant returns to scale. These are obtained by dividing the estimated output elasticities by the returns to scale measure. In other words, the shadow share of each output corresponds to its production elasticity evaluated under the assumption of constant returns to scale.

Table 3 Shadow output and input shares (country samples' average estimates)

Output/Input	Poland		Czechia		Germany		France	
	Coef.	CRS	Coef.	CRS	Coef.	CRS	Coef.	CRS
Cereals	0.390	0.512	0.489	0.581	0.386	0.481	0.346	0.547
Other crop output	0.251	0.330	0.262	0.312	0.234	0.291	0.180	0.285
Other farm output	0.066	0.087	0.034	0.040	0.115	0.143	0.092	0.146
Environmental output	0.054	0.071	0.056	0.067	0.068	0.085	0.014	0.022
Materials	0.407		0.303		0.634		0.418	
Land	0.313		0.352		0.186		0.250	
Labour	0.170		0.227		0.125		0.260	
Capital	0.110		0.118		0.055		0.072	
Economies of scale	1.370		1.288		1.261		1.575	

Source: own calculations

These elasticities reveal a high degree of specialisation in cereal production across all analysed countries. The shadow share of cereals, evaluated at the sample means and adjusted to constant returns to scale, ranges from 48.1 percent in Germany to 58.1 percent in Czechia. At the same time, considerable heterogeneity is observed, particularly with respect to the elasticity of other farm output and environmental output. When evaluated at the sample means, the shadow share of environmental output ranges from 2.2 percent in France to 8.5 percent in Germany, while in Poland and Czechia it is approximately 7 percent. French farms exhibit the lowest share of environmental output in total production. This may indicate that environmental services play a comparatively smaller role in their overall production structure or that they are not fully reflected in environmental subsidies.

Considerable heterogeneity in transformation processes is also evident in the IDF elasticities with respect to inputs, which can be interpreted as input cost shares following Irz and Thirtle (2005). When evaluated at the sample means, materials account for the largest share of total input use in all countries except Czechia, ranging from 40.7 percent in Poland to 63.4 percent in Germany. This highlights the high material intensity of crop production. In Czechia, by contrast, land represents the largest input share, accounting for 35.2 percent, followed by materials at 30.3 percent. This pattern may be related to farm size structure, as Czech farms are, on average, considerably larger than those in the other analysed countries (Table A1 in the Appendix).

Capital accounts for the smallest share among the analysed inputs, ranging from 5.5 percent in Germany to 11.8 percent in Czechia. Overall, these results indicate that crop production with environmental output is, on average, less capital-intensive than labour-intensive across all analysed countries.

Multiple-output flexibility

The IDF estimates enable the computation of the multiple-output flexibility index and its three components: the scope effect, the scale effect, and the convexity effect. Table 4 presents the sample means of the flexibility index and its components, together with statistical tests assessing whether their average values differ significantly from zero. These estimates provide insight into cross-country differences in the transformation process and the capacity of farms to adjust their production structures.

Table 4 Multiple-output flexibility and its components

	Flexibility			Scope effect			Scale effect			Convexity effect		
	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value
Poland	0.155	0.199	0.780	0.316	0.132	2.403**	0.279	0.173	1.618	-0.440	0.101	-4.342***
Czechia	0.124	0.091	1.357	0.481	0.094	5.090***	0.150	0.151	0.993	-0.507	0.031	-16.151***
Germany	0.166	0.066	2.528**	0.407	0.121	3.373***	0.288	0.062	4.616***	-0.529	0.148	-3.575***
France	0.299	0.146	2.315**	0.514	0.268	3.532***	0.302	0.223	1.467	-0.518	0.296	-3.555***

Source: own calculations

Heterogeneity in the transformation process is also reflected in the estimated flexibility index, whose average value ranges from 0.124 in Czechia to 0.299 in France. However, the index is statistically significant only in Germany and France at the 5 percent level. According to Crémieux et al. (2005), a higher value of the flexibility index corresponds to lower multiple output flexibility. In the context of multiple output farms, this reflects greater curvature of the average cost curve when outputs increase proportionally and, consequently, a reduced capacity to adjust or transform the production structure in response to changing market conditions (Renner et al., 2014). Taken together, the results indicate that German farms exhibit a higher degree of flexibility than French farms and therefore possess a stronger ability to adapt their production programmes to changing conditions (Renner et al., 2015), including increasing pressure to improve sustainability through the provision of environmental services.

The flexibility of German farms can be attributed to three cost responses: adjustments in the production structure, referred to as the scope effect, changes in output levels, referred to as the scale effect, and the curvature of marginal costs reflecting resource scarcity, referred to as the convexity effect, as proposed by Renner et al. (2014). For German farms, all three effects are statistically significant at the 5 percent level and, relative to France, German farms exhibit lower values for all three effects. Notably, the convexity effect is the lowest among the analysed countries, suggesting a greater capacity to adjust output levels at relatively low marginal cost. Although the convexity effect in France is only slightly higher, the stronger positive scope effect, indicating diseconomies of scope, together with the scale effect, appears to offset this potential advantage.

A different pattern emerges in Poland, where the convexity effect is the highest while the scope effect is the lowest. This combination may reflect a higher degree of diversification among smaller farms. However, such farms appear to compensate only partially for resource scarcity. The scale effect, which captures cost responsiveness associated with economies of scale achieved through production intensification, is lowest in the Czech Republic, the country characterised by the highest share of large

farms, although this effect is not statistically significant. This result is consistent with the findings of Bokusheva and Čechura (2017), who examined the flexibility of Czech farms over the period 2004 to 2013.

Complementarities or synergies between market production and environmental outputs may arise from more efficient resource use or from improvements in soil productivity and would be reflected in the presence of economies of scope (Chavas, 2008), represented by a negative scope effect. However, for all analysed countries, the estimated scope effect is positive and statistically significant at the 5 percent level. This indicates the presence of diseconomies of scope, meaning that joint production does not generate cost savings. A similar conclusion was reached by Ruijs et al. (2017), who analysed trade-offs between agricultural revenues and non-market outputs, including cultural services, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity, in Central and Eastern European countries using a conditional two-stage semi-parametric frontier approach. Their results suggest that specialisation in agricultural production or in individual ecosystem services may lead to efficiency gains.

The absence of cost complementarities among the analysed farm outputs is further illustrated in Table 5, which shows that all complementarity effects are positive. The only exception is the combination of cereals and other farm output in France; however, the negative effect in this case is not statistically significant.

Table 5 (Dis)Economies of scope

	Poland			Czechia			Germany			France		
	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value	Mean	SD	t-value
Compl.12	0.004	0.050	0.083	0.108	0.021	5.171***	0.038	0.013	2.995***	0.078	0.132	1.559
Compl.13	0.015	0.012	1.282	0.032	0.011	3.042***	0.052	0.013	4.087***	-0.024	0.063	-0.455
Compl.14	0.072	0.021	3.477***	0.051	0.012	4.210***	0.057	0.011	5.043***	0.075	0.024	2.560**
Compl.23	0.013	0.009	1.412	0.019	0.005	3.790***	0.020	0.057	0.358	0.051	0.058	1.228
Compl.24	0.041	0.017	2.449**	0.026	0.006	4.278***	0.026	0.014	1.796*	0.046	0.017	2.761***
Compl.34	0.013	0.005	2.560**	0.005	0.005	0.995	0.011	0.007	1.413	0.031	0.011	2.639***

Source: own calculations

Note: 1 refers to cereal output, 2 to other crop output, 3 to other farm output, and 4 to environmental output.

Regarding the combinations of cereals and other crop output with environmental output, the corresponding effects are statistically significant at least at the 10 percent level in all analysed countries. In contrast, the relationship between other farm output and environmental output is statistically significant only in Poland and France. In France, complementarity effects between environmental output and the remaining outputs are the strongest, which is consistent with the relatively low share of environmental output in the total production. This pattern suggests that environmental output is more costly to integrate into existing production systems. Accordingly, French farms appear to face the weakest incentives to provide environmental output, as its provision leads to more pronounced increases in the marginal costs of market outputs compared with other countries.

Across all countries, the strongest complementarity effect is observed between environmental output and cereals, suggesting that these activities compete intensively for limited resources. This implies limited potential for cost synergies between environmental provision and cereal production.

The role of farm size

Previous research (Renner et al., 2014; Bokusheva and Čechura, 2017) identifies a systematic relationship between farm size and multiple-output flexibility. Building on this strand of the literature, Figure 1 illustrates how flexibility varies across farm size categories in the analysed countries. The

results indicate that small and medium-sized farms attain the highest values of the flexibility index and, therefore, exhibit the lowest degree of flexibility. This implies a reduced ability to adjust their production structure in response to changing conditions. In contrast, larger farms appear to benefit from cost advantages and greater adaptive capacity.

Figure 1 Multiple-output flexibility by farm size category

Source: own calculations

A positive relationship between flexibility and farm size is also reported by Bokusheva and Čechura (2017) for farms in East Germany and Poland over the period 2004 to 2013, whereas Renner et al. (2014) find a negative relationship for Polish farms over the period 1994 to 2001. In the study by Renner et al. (2014), small Polish farms benefited from economies of scale and scope. Similarly, the present analysis indicates that small Polish farms exhibit lower diseconomies of scope. However, this advantage is not sufficient to offset the scale and convexity effects, which ultimately limit their flexibility.

Table 6 provides detailed insights into flexibility and its components across different farm size groups. Consistent with the previous results, flexibility is statistically significant across all size categories only in Germany and France. In both countries, farms larger than 100 hectares are more flexible than those with less than 100 hectares. This greater flexibility is primarily driven by the convexity effect, which suggests that the underlying technology mitigates resource scarcity and reduces the costs associated with adjustments in the scale of operations. By contrast, the scope effect, reflecting pronounced diseconomies of scope, reduces the flexibility of larger farms. For small farms, flexibility is instead constrained by the scale effect. A shift towards the optimal size would generate cost savings for these farms through a reduction in scale inefficiency.

Table 6 Farm flexibility by farm size category

Poland								
	<50 hectares		50–100 hectares		100–500 hectares		>500 hectares	
	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value
Flexibility	0.235	1.086	0.187	0.941	-0.097	-0.490	-0.093	-0.463
Scope eff.	0.260	2.071**	0.287	2.433**	0.595	5.108***	0.610	4.800***
Compl.12	-0.006	-0.116	-0.002	-0.037	0.064	0.905	0.071	0.947
Compl.13	0.014	1.182	0.015	1.271	0.025	1.390	0.025	1.359
Compl.14	0.061	3.329***	0.067	3.706***	0.113	6.836***	0.114	6.845***
Compl.23	0.012	1.279	0.012	1.392	0.018	1.396	0.018	1.360
Compl.24	0.036	2.303**	0.039	2.463**	0.063	3.946***	0.064	4.020***
Compl.34	0.012	2.689***	0.012	2.696***	0.014	2.306**	0.014	2.347**
Scale eff.	0.388	3.147***	0.331	2.469**	-0.177	-1.760*	-0.193	-1.753*
Convexity	-0.414	-3.626***	-0.431	-4.167***	-0.515	-4.022***	-0.510	-3.931***
Czechia								
	<50 hectares		50–100 hectares		100–500 hectares		>500 hectares	
	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value
Flexibility	0.231	9.578***	0.208	6.155***	0.021	0.358	0.009	0.154
Scope eff.	0.398	16.747***	0.409	14.344***	0.581	8.085***	0.603	7.612***
Compl.12	0.085	9.086***	0.090	9.621***	0.133	12.002***	0.136	11.443***
Compl.13	0.028	5.648***	0.027	5.093***	0.038	2.954***	0.041	3.165***
Compl.14	0.044	7.544***	0.045	6.673***	0.061	4.917***	0.063	5.101***
Compl.23	0.016	6.438***	0.016	5.723***	0.022	4.279***	0.023	4.234***
Compl.24	0.021	6.168***	0.022	6.199***	0.031	5.855***	0.032	5.627***
Compl.34	0.005	3.786***	0.004	1.954*	0.005	0.784	0.006	0.946
Scale eff.	0.312	8.507***	0.283	6.591***	-0.031	-0.388	-0.058	-0.645
Convexity	-0.480	-32.922***	-0.485	-27.870***	-0.530	-17.845***	-0.537	-17.602***
Germany								
	<50 hectares		50–100 hectares		100–500 hectares		>500 hectares	
	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value
Flexibility	0.188	4.237***	0.187	3.794***	0.125	2.288***	0.122	2.321**
Scope eff.	0.377	4.990***	0.385	4.029***	0.449	2.705***	0.459	2.490**
Compl.12	0.040	3.681***	0.039	3.745***	0.031	3.199***	0.027	2.422**
Compl.13	0.049	4.021***	0.049	4.187***	0.060	5.305***	0.065	4.712***
Compl.14	0.054	4.781***	0.055	4.821***	0.062	6.925***	0.062	6.078***
Compl.23	0.012	0.434	0.014	0.335	0.036	0.419	0.038	0.396
Compl.24	0.027	2.995***	0.029	2.603***	0.017	1.357	0.016	1.299
Compl.34	0.006	1.173	0.007	1.257	0.019	2.583***	0.021	2.620***
Scale eff.	0.309	4.992***	0.302	4.767***	0.271	4.977***	0.263	4.873***
Convexity	-0.498	-7.048***	-0.500	-4.889***	-0.595	-3.005***	-0.600	-2.776***
France								
	<50 hectares		50–100 hectares		100–500 hectares		>500 hectares	
	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value
Flexibility	0.494	4.482***	0.407	3.679***	0.114	1.961**	0.114	1.961**
Scope eff.	0.385	1.257	0.418	2.824***	0.843	6.042***	0.843	6.042***
Compl.12	0.086	0.674	0.078	1.232	0.121	2.037**	0.121	2.037**
Compl.13	-0.062	-0.588	-0.044	-0.750	-0.010	-0.193	-0.010	-0.193
Compl.14	0.048	2.002**	0.054	2.336**	0.114	5.140***	0.114	5.140***
Compl.23	0.065	0.526	0.054	0.971	0.101	1.526	0.101	1.526
Compl.24	0.036	1.622	0.042	2.472**	0.039	3.117***	0.039	3.117***
Compl.34	0.019	1.667*	0.025	2.393***	0.057	8.363***	0.057	8.363***
Scale eff.	0.609	5.048***	0.488	3.455***	-0.032	-0.234	-0.032	-0.234
Convexity	-0.500	-1.382	-0.498	-2.727***	-0.697	-3.874***	-0.697	-3.874***

Source: own calculations

Note: Statistical significance is denoted as follows: *** for 1%, ** for 5%, and * for 10%.

Across all analysed countries, farms smaller than 100 hectares exhibit a lower scope effect than farms larger than 100 hectares, indicating a stronger presence of diseconomies of scope among larger farms. The positive relationship between farm size and diseconomies of scope is further confirmed by the panel regression results presented in Table A4 in the Appendix. The effect of farm size is statistically insignificant only in the case of German farms, even at the 10 percent significance level. With the exception of Germany, higher multifactor productivity and greater labour intensity are positively associated with diseconomies of scope. This pattern may reflect a higher degree of specialisation among more productive and more labour-intensive farms. Based on the results of Bokusheva and Čechura (2017), a positive association with the intensity of chemical inputs, including fertilisers and

pesticides, and a negative association with location in areas facing natural constraints were expected. However, the coefficients of these determinants are not statistically significant, even at the 10 percent level.

A more detailed decomposition into individual complementarity effects reveals pronounced competition rather than synergy between market outputs, particularly cereals, and environmental output. Although some complementarity effects appear negative at a more disaggregated level, they are neither associated with environmental output, nor statistically significant.

Figures 3 to 6 further illustrate that negative values, representing complementarity between market and environmental outputs, occur only as outliers. When such observations appear, they are more frequently associated with other farm outputs than with crop production. In contrast, positive values, reflecting higher costs of joint production, are more prevalent among larger farms, thereby potentially reducing their incentives to provide environmental outputs. These findings do not support the presence of windfall effects associated with participation in environmental subsidy schemes.

Figure 3 Complementarity with environmental output by farm size category – Poland

Source: own calculations

Figure 4 Complementarity with environmental output by farm size category – Czechia

Source: own calculations

Figure 5 Complementarity with environmental output by farm size category – Germany

Source: own calculations

Figure 6 Complementarity with environmental output by farm size category – France

Source: own calculations

Since the strongest complementarity effect is observed between environmental output and cereals, an additional panel regression is estimated to further examine the significance of the relationship between farm size and complementarity for this specific output combination. However, Table A5 in the Appendix shows that this relationship is statistically significant at the 5 percent level only in the case of France.

In France, complementarity is also negatively associated with farms located at altitudes above 600 metres and in areas facing natural constraints. A similar negative association with areas facing natural constraints is observed in Poland. For these farms, the production of environmental outputs appears to involve a lower trade-off, as they cannot achieve the same level of cost efficiency through intensification as farms located in more productive regions. Their lower productivity implies lower opportunity costs, as the foregone utility from adopting environmentally friendly practices, relative to alternative land uses or more intensive production methods, is smaller, as noted by Schaub et al. (2023).

Robustness check

To assess the robustness of the results, the input distance function is re-estimated using an alternative output aggregation. In this specification, cereal output and other crop output are combined into a single crop category. The estimation results of the input distance function are reported in Table A6 in the Appendix, while detailed attention is devoted to flexibility and its components in Table 7.

Table 7 Multiple-output flexibility and its components (IDF with three outputs)

	Poland		Czechia		Germany		France	
	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value	Mean	t-value
Flexibility	0.382	3.600***	0.129	0.933	0.218	1.081	0.396	2.839***
Scope effect	0.298	5.921***	0.440	3.569***	0.282	3.483***	0.357	3.594***
Compl.12	0.036	2.177**	0.054	1.722	0.066	2.165**	0.028	1.701*
Compl.13	0.096	5.736***	0.146	3.853***	0.066	3.286***	0.118	3.085***
Compl.23	0.016	2.697***	0.012	2.577**	0.009	2.105**	0.032	2.171**
Scale effect	0.345	2.507**	0.091	0.378	0.222	0.926	0.336	1.631*
Convexity effect	-0.260	-7.032***	-0.401	-1.755*	-0.287	-2.308**	-0.297	-7.907***

Source: own calculations

Note: 1 refers to crop output, 2 to other farm output, and 3 to environmental output.

The change in output aggregation modifies the statistical significance of the flexibility index. Consistent with the results reported in Table 4, the index remains statistically significant for French farms. However, instead of German farms, it is now statistically significant for Polish farms.

In line with Table 4, French farms record the highest average flexibility index among the analysed countries, implying the lowest degree of flexibility. The scope effect remains statistically significant at the 10 percent level across all analysed countries. It attains its lowest value in Germany and its highest in Czechia. The scale effect is statistically significant only in Poland and France and, consistent with Table 4, reaches its highest magnitude in France. The convexity effect is statistically significant in all analysed countries, with the lowest value observed in Poland, again corresponding to the findings in Table 4. Finally, complementarity effects are positive in every country and indicate stronger competitive relationships between crop outputs and environmental output. This finding confirms that no synergies arise between the provision of environmental output and the production of market outputs when evaluated at the sample means.

Policy implications

Modelling the production process with environmental output and analysing farm flexibility provides valuable insights for agricultural policymakers. In the European Union, policy incentives aimed at fostering sustainable farming and protecting the environment have a long-standing tradition, with increasing emphasis particularly since the 2014 to 2020 programming period (Castaldo et al., 2025). Nevertheless, substantial differences in their uptake persist across Member States (Podruzik and Fertő, 2024). The results reveal considerable heterogeneity in the provision of environmental output and the corresponding technologies among crop farms across European countries. Such heterogeneity should be explicitly considered in the design of environmental payments, as differences in production technologies are likely to translate into heterogeneous behavioural responses to identical policy incentives.

The provision of environmental outputs has important implications for farm economic performance. Castaldo et al. (2025), analysing 22 EU Member States over the period 2006 to 2013, show that farms participating in agri-environmental measures improved their productivity despite facing higher costs. This effect may be attributed to land augmenting technical change, which generates additional productivity growth. Environmentally friendly practices may, for instance, enhance soil quality and fertility (Diop and Védrine, 2025). Mennig and Sauer (2020), in contrast, argue that participation in such schemes may reduce production costs associated with specific inputs, including energy, labour, and chemicals. However, the productivity effects of participation are not uniform across farm types (Biagini et al., 2023), reinforcing the importance of accounting for structural and technological heterogeneity.

From a flexibility perspective, positive performance effects of environmentally friendly practices may create complementarities between market and environmental outputs. If such complementarities exist, environmental payments may partly generate windfall effects, thereby reducing the cost-effectiveness of environmental measures, as public support would remunerate practices that farms would have adopted even in the absence of payments (Chabé Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Diop et al., 2024; Diop and Védrine, 2025). However, the results do not provide evidence of cost complementarities between market and environmental outputs. The provision of environmental output does not appear to generate a cost advantage for crop farms, suggesting that additional concerns may be more closely linked to policy design than to inherent technological synergies.

The role of farm size further refines these conclusions. The joint production of market and environmental outputs is more costly for larger farms. In line with Matthews (2013) and Schaub et al.

(2023), stronger or better targeted incentives may therefore be required to encourage large farms to provide environmental outputs. Conversely, small farms exhibit lower flexibility, which increases their vulnerability to changing conditions and places them at the forefront of policymakers' attention.

Policy implications follow directly from these findings. The design of environmental payments should better reflect technological and structural heterogeneity, potentially through differentiated payment levels or country-specific, or even region-specific, targeting. Previous studies, such as Ruijs et al. (2017), highlight substantial regional differences in trade-offs between ecosystem services, suggesting that individual regions may hold a comparative advantage in the provision of specific services. This further supports the case for more spatially differentiated policy design. At the same time, policy instruments should balance efficiency and equity considerations. Larger farms may require stronger incentives due to higher adjustment costs, whereas smaller farms may need supportive measures that enhance adaptive capacity and flexibility. Overall, a more targeted policy design could improve both the cost-effectiveness and the environmental performance of environmental payment schemes.

Conclusions

In response to growing environmental concerns and increasing pressure to enhance the sustainability of agricultural production, this study investigates agri-environmental commitments of crop farms in four EU Member States, Poland, Czechia, Germany, and France. Using the system GMM estimator applied to FADN data covering the period 2008 to 2021, the study estimates production technology represented by an input distance function incorporating both environmental and market outputs. It then measures multiple-output flexibility and its components and assesses farmers' incentives for the joint production of environmental and market outputs within the framework of economies of scope, with particular emphasis on the role of farm size.

The results reveal substantial cross-country heterogeneity in production technologies. In terms of environmental output provision, France displays the lowest relative orientation, whereas Germany shows the highest. Consistent with this pattern, German farms exhibit the greatest degree of flexibility, indicating a stronger capacity to adjust production programmes in response to changing economic and policy conditions, including increasing pressure to enhance sustainability through the provision of environmental services.

Across all countries, the findings indicate the presence of diseconomies of scope, suggesting that the joint production of environmental and market outputs does not generate cost savings. Consequently, the observed production structures offer only limited diversification benefits, including with respect to environmental output provision. Compared with farms in the other analysed countries, French farms appear to face weaker economic incentives to supply environmental outputs, as their provision increases the marginal costs of market outputs more substantially.

The strongest competition for resources is observed between environmental output and cereals across all countries. This indicates that these activities compete more intensively than other output combinations and that environmental provision does not generate cost synergies with cereal production.

Farm size further differentiates these effects. Larger farms display stronger diseconomies of scope and therefore weaker incentives to adjust their production structures in response to environmental output provision. This relationship is particularly pronounced in France, where higher levels of environmental output are more likely among farms located in areas facing natural constraints and mountainous

regions. In contrast, small farms exhibit lower flexibility and, consequently, a more limited capacity to adapt their production structures to changing conditions.

These findings contribute to the literature by providing empirical evidence that environmental and market outputs are characterised by cost trade-offs rather than complementarities, with important implications for policy design. Environmental payment schemes should more explicitly account for technological and structural heterogeneity across farms. Policy design should also balance efficiency and equity considerations. Larger farms may require stronger incentives to compensate for higher adjustment costs, whereas smaller farms may benefit more from measures that enhance adaptive capacity and flexibility. Overall, a more targeted and flexibility-sensitive policy approach could strengthen both the cost-effectiveness and the environmental performance of agri-environmental policy.

Despite relying on a robust empirical framework, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the analysis assumes that environmental output is fully captured by environmental subsidies. In practice, some farms may provide environmental services without participating in support schemes, meaning that such provision is not fully captured in the data and may introduce measurement bias. Second, the dataset spans multiple programming periods during which environmental outputs were valued and supported differently, potentially introducing unobserved heterogeneity in incentives and compensation levels. Finally, the analysis assumes a common production technology for crop farms within each country. Relaxing this assumption and allowing for greater technological heterogeneity would provide more accurate and policy-relevant insights. Addressing these limitations represents an important avenue for future research.

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Appendix

Table A1 Descriptive statistics of variables used in analysis

Variable	Poland		Czechia		Germany		France	
	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev
Cereals [Eur]	51724.9	143284.8	256863.5	408409.5	127686.0	271061.6	104357.1	70282.2
Other crop output [Eur]	44595.1	128646.8	286181.1	534492.5	134989.6	258970.4	73243.2	74474.6
Other farm output [Eur]	10204.3	32153.4	105504.4	336465.3	46487.2	177850.9	22354.7	31631.9
Environmental output [Eur]	3861.4	9271.5	26408.1	51517.3	11961.1	26180.7	5676.2	7600.5
Materials [Eur]	63530.3	179295.4	431076.1	718160.4	172481.2	336261.9	114140.9	69531.1
Land [hectare]	87.3	187.8	479.9	652.9	190.4	358.9	138.6	80.9
Labour [AWU]	2.7	4.8	9.6	16.9	2.6	5.2	1.7	1.0
Capital [Eur]	19520.1	51989.6	104666.3	161630.5	59514.7	91086.2	51524.7	36505.8

Source: Own processing

Table A2 Description of factors of multiple-output flexibility (means and proportions)

Variable	Description (FADN code)	Poland		Czechia		Germany		France	
		Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean	Std.Dev
Farm size	Total utilized area (SE025)	87.31	187.81	479.86	652.87	190.41	358.86	138.58	80.91
Unpaid labour share	Share of unpaid labour (SE015/SE010)	0.86	0.26	0.52	0.45	0.79	0.30	0.86	0.21
Rented land share	Share of rented land (SE030/SE025)	0.28	0.26	0.72	0.25	0.61	0.28	0.87	0.23
Multifactor productivity	Total output divided total input (SE131/SE270)	1.23	0.36	1.01	0.28	1.04	0.28	1.02	0.24
Non-agri output share	Share of other (non-agricultural) output on total output (SE256/SE131)	0.02	0.06	0.05	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.08
Fertiliser intensity	Expenditure per hectare in fertilisers (SE295/SE025)	187.80	91.59	135.70	64.94	193.68	105.50	215.45	77.45
Pesticide intensity	Expenditure per hectare in pesticides (SE300/SE025)	85.57	54.61	131.04	71.50	168.86	128.36	167.60	63.84
Labour intensity	Labour input per 100 hectares (SE010/SE025/100)	6.76	6.81	2.40	3.51	2.47	4.57	1.48	0.97
Fixed assets intensity	Fixed assets per hectare (deflated SE441/SE025), ipi_fix.assets (2010=100)	6493.61	3530.38	1985.03	1650.50	9518.20	8872.14	1848.75	1353.00
Field crops farms	1 for TF16	46.21		26.63		40.06		28.35	
Mixed farms	1 for TF60	6.74		2.48		7.07		4.58	
Organic farm	1 for organic farming management	1.14		1.48		2.63		2.12	
Altitude 300–600	1 for altitude 300 to 600m a.s.l.	15.35		36.03		19.46		8.39	
Altitude >600	1 for altitude above 600m a.s.l.	2.37		1.04		1.00		0.69	
ANC	1 for natural and other specific constrains (ANC)	33.30		18.95		20.09		24.45	
LFA	1 for mountain less-favoured areas (LFA)	0.27		1.09		0.30		1.22	

Source: Own processing

Table A3 IDF parameter estimates

Variable	Poland			Czechia			Germany			France		
	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t
Cereals	-0.390	0.012	0.000	-0.489	0.022	0.000	-0.386	0.027	0.000	-0.346	0.026	0.000
O_Crops	-0.251	0.010	0.000	-0.262	0.024	0.000	-0.234	0.018	0.000	-0.180	0.013	0.000
O_F_Output	-0.066	0.006	0.000	-0.034	0.005	0.000	-0.115	0.012	0.000	-0.092	0.008	0.000
Envi_Output	-0.054	0.005	0.000	-0.056	0.010	0.000	-0.068	0.019	0.000	-0.014	0.003	0.000
Land	0.313	0.023	0.000	0.352	0.047	0.000	0.186	0.056	0.001	0.250	0.041	0.000
Labour	0.170	0.016	0.000	0.227	0.031	0.000	0.125	0.041	0.002	0.260	0.027	0.000
Capital	0.110	0.014	0.000	0.118	0.018	0.000	0.055	0.030	0.072	0.072	0.020	0.000
Time	0.028	0.003	0.000	0.030	0.020	0.134	0.266	0.021	0.000	0.011	0.007	0.102
Cereals ²	-0.101	0.018	0.000	-0.050	0.003	0.000	-0.042	0.005	0.000	-0.200	0.046	0.000
O_Crops ²	-0.082	0.009	0.000	-0.027	0.003	0.000	-0.018	0.003	0.000	-0.049	0.011	0.000
O_F_Output ²	-0.018	0.004	0.000	-0.008	0.002	0.000	-0.014	0.002	0.000	-0.029	0.004	0.000
Envi_Output ²	-0.026	0.003	0.000	-0.012	0.002	0.000	-0.017	0.005	0.001	-0.039	0.006	0.000
Land ²	-0.186	0.077	0.015	-0.371	0.112	0.001	-0.472	0.131	0.000	0.046	0.153	0.764
Labour ²	0.003	0.052	0.948	0.105	0.074	0.160	-0.013	0.123	0.918	-0.123	0.067	0.066
Capital ²	0.041	0.043	0.345	-0.007	0.048	0.884	-0.011	0.083	0.896	0.039	0.055	0.476
Time ³	-0.004	0.002	0.098	0.022	0.006	0.000	0.093	0.007	0.000	-0.007	0.003	0.038
CerealsXO_Crops	0.053	0.011	0.000	0.018	0.005	0.000	0.039	0.008	0.000	0.026	0.019	0.175
CerealsXO_F_Output	0.010	0.007	0.184	0.001	0.001	0.333	-0.001	0.003	0.831	-0.001	0.011	0.934
CerealsXEnvi_Output	0.004	0.002	0.008	-0.001	0.001	0.539	0.002	0.002	0.198	0.014	0.003	0.000
O_CropsXO_F_Output	0.004	0.005	0.469	-0.001	0.001	0.352	-0.003	0.005	0.555	0.007	0.005	0.213
O_CropsXEnvi_Output	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.065	0.006	0.003	0.041	0.003	0.001	0.044
O_F_OutputXEnvi_Out	0.001	0.001	0.266	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.294	0.001	0.001	0.046
LandXLabour	0.090	0.045	0.045	-0.055	0.057	0.340	0.254	0.075	0.001	-0.009	0.075	0.902
LandXCapital	0.062	0.048	0.197	0.059	0.046	0.200	0.191	0.106	0.071	-0.015	0.058	0.790
LabourXCapital	-0.021	0.035	0.556	-0.029	0.038	0.437	-0.138	0.077	0.071	0.029	0.046	0.530
CerealsXLand	0.041	0.029	0.160	0.018	0.011	0.112	0.037	0.019	0.049	-0.053	0.064	0.403
CerealsXLabour	-0.011	0.027	0.679	0.003	0.021	0.882	-0.027	0.019	0.158	-0.106	0.043	0.013
CerealsXCapital	0.014	0.022	0.515	-0.007	0.004	0.110	-0.015	0.022	0.501	0.059	0.031	0.057
O_CropXLand	0.038	0.023	0.101	0.009	0.005	0.046	-0.031	0.030	0.290	0.069	0.034	0.043
O_CropXLabour	0.001	0.015	0.922	-0.008	0.011	0.472	0.051	0.020	0.009	-0.009	0.024	0.718
O_CropXCapital	0.003	0.017	0.865	0.002	0.014	0.911	-0.026	0.021	0.232	-0.024	0.020	0.226
O_F_OutputXLand	-0.017	0.014	0.216	-0.007	0.004	0.047	0.004	0.015	0.801	-0.054	0.018	0.003
O_F_OutputXLabour	-0.003	0.010	0.794	-0.008	0.003	0.006	0.009	0.013	0.510	0.007	0.014	0.629
O_F_OutputXCapital	0.009	0.009	0.292	-0.005	0.006	0.443	0.030	0.014	0.036	0.023	0.009	0.012
Envi_OutputXLand	0.008	0.003	0.013	0.000	0.006	0.977	0.017	0.007	0.024	0.003	0.004	0.366
Envi_OutputXLabour	-0.002	0.002	0.300	0.004	0.003	0.190	0.002	0.004	0.597	0.000	0.002	0.942
Envi_OutputXCapital	-0.005	0.002	0.028	-0.004	0.003	0.107	-0.006	0.004	0.149	-0.002	0.002	0.186
CerealsXTime	0.004	0.003	0.249	0.002	0.001	0.236	-0.007	0.003	0.041	-0.005	0.006	0.371
O_CropXTime	-0.001	0.002	0.576	0.002	0.002	0.385	0.004	0.003	0.182	-0.007	0.003	0.029
O_F_OutputXTime	0.000	0.001	0.770	-0.001	0.000	0.110	0.004	0.002	0.042	0.001	0.002	0.521
Envi_OutputXTime	0.000	0.001	0.967	-0.002	0.001	0.007	-0.003	0.002	0.120	0.006	0.001	0.000
LandXTime	-0.001	0.007	0.827	0.002	0.008	0.773	0.030	0.011	0.007	0.017	0.007	0.025
LabourXTime	0.000	0.004	0.983	0.001	0.005	0.844	-0.007	0.007	0.313	-0.010	0.005	0.041
CapitalXTime	0.002	0.004	0.565	-0.002	0.004	0.724	0.886	0.123	0.000	0.009	0.005	0.069
Constant	0.795	0.067	0.000	0.627	0.059	0.000	-0.121	0.088	0.169	1.154	0.167	0.000
Year_2015	0.023	0.015	0.141	0.317	0.061	0.000	-0.401	0.111	0.000	0.262	0.039	0.000
Year_2016	-0.022	0.019	0.238	0.334	0.083	0.000	-0.814	0.140	0.000	0.142	0.031	0.000
Year_2017	-0.020	0.018	0.280	0.240	0.109	0.029	-1.418	0.177	0.000	0.149	0.019	0.000
Year_2018	-0.044	0.017	0.011	0.157	0.146	0.281	-1.981	0.220	0.000	0.061	0.012	0.000
Year_2019	-0.089	0.013	0.000	0.008	0.188	0.966	-2.625	0.272	0.000			
Year_2020				-0.045	0.236	0.848	-3.527	0.328	0.000			
Year_2021				-0.181	0.292	0.536	-0.121	0.088	0.169			
D_Altitude_more_600										-0.232	0.185	0.209
D_Field_crops_farms										0.098	0.032	0.002
Economies of scale	1.370			1.288			1.261			1.575		
AR(2)-test	0.11		0.911	-1.67		0.095	-0.34		0.733	1.78		0.075
Hansen test	1193.84	Chi2(1156)	0.214	424.42	Chi2(422)	0.458	175.45	Chi2(160)	0.191	604.86	Chi2(571)	0.158
F-test	1605.44	F(49,1404)	0.000	660.54	F(51,460)	0.000	160.14	F(51,1987)	0.000	246.92	F(50,1410)	0.000
F-test: translog	26.11	F(36,1404)	0.000	121.01	F(36,460)	0.000	47.43	F(36,1987)	0.000	14.70	F(36,1410)	0.000
N. instruments	1206			474			212			622		
N. groups	1405			461			1988			1411		

Source: own calculations

Table A4 Determinants of (dis)economies of scope

Variable	Poland			Czechia			Germany			France		
	Coef.	Std.E	P> t									
Farm_size	0.266	0.048	0.000	0.103	0.035	0.003	-0.003	0.038	0.933	1.078	0.040	0.000
Unpaid_labour_share	-0.065	0.026	0.012	-0.009	0.011	0.417				-0.070	0.013	0.000
MFP	0.034	0.006	0.000	0.041	0.004	0.000	-0.045	0.019	0.017	0.167	0.012	0.000
Fertiliser_intensity	0.251	0.026	0.000									
Pesticide_intensity	0.341	0.048	0.000									
Labour_intensity	0.009	0.002	0.000	0.017	0.004	0.000	-0.072	0.013	0.000	0.031	0.005	0.000
Mean_Farm_size	-0.061	0.055	0.274	-0.015	0.038	0.694	0.028	0.038	0.458			
Mean_Unpaid_labour_share	-0.050	0.029	0.085	-0.085	0.016	0.000						
Mean_MFP	0.028	0.011	0.008	-0.016	0.012	0.208	0.037	0.021	0.076			
Mean_Fertiliser_intensity	0.118	0.048	0.015									
Mean_Pesticide_intensity	0.198	0.079	0.013									
Mean_Labour_intensity	-0.011	0.002	0.000	-0.008	0.004	0.071	0.033	0.013	0.012			
D_ANC							0.007	0.004	0.091			
D_Field_crops_farms	0.027	0.004	0.000	0.007	0.004	0.051	0.005	0.004	0.177	-0.006	0.008	0.421
D_Mixed_farms	0.018	0.012	0.142	0.008	0.009	0.380	0.008	0.011	0.480	-0.030	0.010	0.002
Year_2009	0.014	0.015	0.351	0.023	0.004	0.000	-0.028	0.017	0.102	0.046	0.082	0.577
Year_2010	-0.008	0.015	0.585	0.016	0.006	0.007	-0.019	0.014	0.156	-0.037	0.038	0.333
Year_2011	-0.034	0.015	0.018	0.000	0.004	0.910	0.005	0.014	0.704	-0.142	0.034	0.000
Year_2012	-0.025	0.015	0.098	-0.003	0.005	0.492	-0.020	0.015	0.188	-0.129	0.034	0.000
Year_2013	-0.019	0.014	0.175	-0.001	0.005	0.771	-0.017	0.015	0.244	-0.114	0.041	0.006
Year_2014	-0.012	0.015	0.408	0.000	0.005	0.989	-0.025	0.015	0.096	-0.167	0.033	0.000
Year_2015	-0.016	0.014	0.245	0.030	0.005	0.000	-0.021	0.014	0.132	-0.130	0.032	0.000
Year_2016	-0.021	0.014	0.121	0.035	0.006	0.000	-0.016	0.014	0.262	-0.147	0.032	0.000
Year_2017	-0.023	0.014	0.097	0.031	0.005	0.000	-0.019	0.014	0.172	-0.152	0.032	0.000
Year_2018	-0.026	0.014	0.054	0.034	0.005	0.000	-0.017	0.014	0.240	-0.148	0.032	0.000
Year_2019	-0.038	0.014	0.006	0.029	0.005	0.000	-0.017	0.014	0.215	-0.149	0.032	0.000
Year_2020	-0.032	0.014	0.024	0.034	0.006	0.000	-0.022	0.014	0.130	-0.165	0.032	0.000
Year_2021	-0.045	0.014	0.002	0.027	0.006	0.000	-0.015	0.013	0.256	-0.196	0.032	0.000
Constant	0.226	0.022	0.000	0.417	0.017	0.000	0.473	0.017	0.000	0.347	0.038	0.000
Wald-test	1960.92	Chi2(27)	0.000	941.60	Chi2(23)	0.000	300.75	Chi2(22)	0.000	1976.47	Chi2(19)	0.000
Wald-test: Mundlak	65.21	Chi2(6)	0.000	37.29	Chi2(4)	0.000	7.12	Chi2(3)	0.068	0.47	Chi2(4)	0.977
Wald-test IV for MFP, Labour_intensity, Fertiliser_intensity, Pesticide_intensity	4.15	Chi2(4)	0.386	1.72	Chi2(2)	0.424	0.53	Chi2(2)	0.766	1.52	Chi2(2)	0.467
Hausman-test										18.96	Chi2(17)	0.331

Source: own calculations

Table A5 Determinants of complementary effect cereals vs. environmental output

Variable	Poland			Czechia			Germany			France		
	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t
Farm_size	0.009	0.010	0.374	0.005	0.008	0.536	-0.004	0.002	0.061	0.289	0.035	0.000
Unpaid_labour_share				-0.004	0.003	0.107				-0.012	0.004	0.007
MFP	-0.004	0.001	0.000				-0.006	0.001	0.000	0.037	0.002	0.000
Fertiliser_intensity	0.006	0.004	0.091									
Labour_intensity	-0.001	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.009	0.002	0.000
Fixed_assets_intensity				-0.001	0.000	0.063						
Mean_Farm_size	0.027	0.010	0.005				0.007	0.002	0.000	-0.049	0.036	0.181
Mean_Unpaid_labour_share										0.002	0.006	0.676
Mean_MFP	-0.002	0.002	0.144				-0.001	0.001	0.139	-0.001	0.004	0.826
Mean_Fertiliser_intensity	0.018	0.006	0.003									
Mean_Labour_intensity	-0.001	0.000	0.000				-0.001	0.001	0.054	-0.005	0.002	0.018
D_Altitude_more_600										-0.014	0.006	0.015
D_ANC	-0.002	0.001	0.007							-0.011	0.001	0.000
D_Field_crops_farms	-0.008	0.001	0.000				-0.003	0.000	0.000	-0.016	0.003	0.000
D_Mixed_farms	-0.011	0.002	0.000				-0.001	0.001	0.260	0.031	0.010	0.001
Year_2009	-0.004	0.002	0.039	0.001	0.001	0.139	0.002	0.001	0.038	0.022	0.006	0.000
Year_2010	0.001	0.002	0.529	0.002	0.001	0.053	0.006	0.001	0.000	0.003	0.006	0.621
Year_2011	-0.001	0.002	0.756	0.001	0.001	0.215	0.008	0.001	0.000	0.006	0.006	0.264
Year_2012	-0.002	0.002	0.276	0.001	0.001	0.125	0.008	0.001	0.000	0.010	0.006	0.076
Year_2013	-0.006	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.515	0.010	0.001	0.000	0.011	0.006	0.066
Year_2014	-0.003	0.002	0.059	0.001	0.001	0.222	0.011	0.001	0.000	0.024	0.006	0.000
Year_2015	-0.002	0.002	0.303	0.011	0.001	0.000	0.022	0.001	0.000	0.014	0.006	0.013
Year_2016	-0.003	0.002	0.109	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.025	0.001	0.000	0.021	0.006	0.000
Year_2017	-0.004	0.002	0.035	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.026	0.001	0.000	0.022	0.006	0.000
Year_2018	-0.003	0.002	0.126	0.014	0.001	0.000	0.029	0.001	0.000	0.025	0.006	0.000
Year_2019	-0.003	0.002	0.094	0.014	0.001	0.000	0.033	0.001	0.000	0.017	0.006	0.002
Year_2020	-0.004	0.002	0.024	0.014	0.001	0.000	0.034	0.001	0.000	0.011	0.006	0.043
Year_2021	-0.006	0.002	0.001	0.015	0.001	0.000	0.036	0.001	0.000	-0.013	0.008	0.120
Constant	0.089	0.003	0.000	0.038	0.005	0.000	0.038	0.001	0.000	-0.011	0.001	0.000
F-test				21.75	Chi2(17,23 9)	0.000						
Wald-test	1751.14	Chi2(24)	0.000				6844.68	Chi2(21)	0.000	2121.93	Chi2(24)	0.000
Wald-test: Mundlak	42.48	Chi2(4)	0.000	7.09	Chi2(4)	0.131	26.45	Chi2(3)	0.000	8.69	Chi2(4)	0.069
Wald-test: IV_MFP, IV_Labour_intensity	1.20	Chi2(3)	0.753	0.16	F(1,138)	0.689	4.11	Chi2(2)	0.128	4.16	Chi2(2)	0.125
Hausman-test				51.07	Chi2(17)	0.000						

Source: own calculations

Table A6 IDF parameter estimates – three outputs

Variable	Poland			Czechia			Germany			France		
	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t	Coef.	Std.E	P> t
Crop	-0.622	0.016	0.000	-0.676	0.023	0.000	-0.678	0.013	0.000	-0.467	0.035	0.000
O_Output	-0.083	0.007	0.000	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.080	0.006	0.000	-0.099	0.008	0.000
Envi_Output	-0.053	0.005	0.000	-0.114	0.013	0.000	-0.046	0.006	0.000	-0.019	0.004	0.000
Land	0.212	0.023	0.000	0.300	0.042	0.000	0.144	0.031	0.000	0.247	0.045	0.000
Labour	0.215	0.019	0.000	0.288	0.026	0.000	0.222	0.018	0.000	0.280	0.025	0.000
Capital	0.134	0.016	0.000	0.081	0.019	0.000	0.140	0.018	0.000	0.082	0.016	0.000
Time	0.029	0.003	0.000	0.035	0.015	0.021	0.061	0.006	0.000	0.022	0.008	0.007
Crop ²	-0.103	0.021	0.000	-0.110	0.024	0.000	-0.111	0.021	0.000	-0.225	0.064	0.000
O_Output ²	-0.026	0.004	0.000	-0.009	0.001	0.000	-0.009	0.001	0.000	-0.034	0.005	0.000
Envi_Output ²	-0.025	0.003	0.000	-0.026	0.003	0.000	-0.010	0.002	0.000	-0.045	0.007	0.000
Land ²	-0.098	0.072	0.171	0.145	0.079	0.066	-0.012	0.057	0.837	0.033	0.148	0.823
Labour ²	0.094	0.040	0.020	-0.068	0.071	0.340	0.059	0.043	0.175	-0.097	0.082	0.235
Capital ²	0.072	0.041	0.081	0.018	0.048	0.708	0.117	0.039	0.003	-0.031	0.055	0.572
Time ²	-0.002	0.001	0.248	0.031	0.005	0.000	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.012	0.004	0.005
CropXO_Output	0.022	0.008	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.545	-0.002	0.005	0.646	0.019	0.012	0.103
CropXEnvi_Output	0.010	0.002	0.000	0.017	0.002	0.000	0.004	0.001	0.004	0.014	0.004	0.000
O_OutputXEnvi_Out	0.001	0.001	0.112	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.798	0.003	0.001	0.001
LandXLabour	-0.073	0.042	0.085	-0.220	0.051	0.000	-0.050	0.035	0.153	-0.003	0.077	0.966
LandXCapital	0.118	0.043	0.006	-0.031	0.042	0.464	-0.020	0.036	0.570	-0.028	0.063	0.656
LabourXCapital	0.030	0.035	0.397	-0.053	0.048	0.265	-0.071	0.032	0.027	0.016	0.046	0.732
CropXLand	0.007	0.033	0.820	-0.109	0.030	0.000	-0.057	0.021	0.007	0.047	0.064	0.460
CropXLabour	0.003	0.023	0.909	-0.038	0.033	0.262	0.002	0.022	0.923	-0.118	0.057	0.040
CropXCapital	0.062	0.023	0.008	0.005	0.024	0.849	0.041	0.020	0.037	-0.002	0.033	0.944
O_OutputXLand	-0.010	0.015	0.501	0.010	0.004	0.022	0.009	0.007	0.209	-0.033	0.020	0.108
O_OutputXLabour	-0.005	0.010	0.615	-0.006	0.004	0.152	-0.011	0.006	0.062	0.018	0.015	0.233
O_OutputXCapital	0.020	0.008	0.017	-0.001	0.003	0.835	0.001	0.004	0.789	0.013	0.012	0.298
Envi_OutputXLand	0.012	0.003	0.000	0.014	0.003	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.558	0.008	0.005	0.117
Envi_OutputXLabour	-0.001	0.002	0.646	0.003	0.003	0.267	0.004	0.002	0.055	-0.006	0.002	0.004
Envi_OutputXCapital	-0.002	0.002	0.369	-0.005	0.002	0.040	0.000	0.002	0.964	-0.002	0.002	0.259
CropXTime	-0.003	0.003	0.402	0.001	0.002	0.674	0.005	0.003	0.050	-0.015	0.006	0.012
O_OutputXTime	-0.001	0.002	0.483	0.000	0.000	0.464	0.000	0.001	0.978	-0.001	0.002	0.650
Envi_OutputXTime	-0.001	0.001	0.036	-0.003	0.001	0.000	-0.004	0.001	0.003	0.009	0.002	0.000
LandXTime	0.006	0.006	0.288	0.008	0.005	0.123	0.008	0.004	0.084	0.007	0.009	0.485
LabourXTime	-0.008	0.004	0.044	-0.016	0.004	0.000	-0.004	0.004	0.291	-0.002	0.004	0.729
CapitalXTime	-0.004	0.005	0.418	0.003	0.004	0.507	-0.004	0.005	0.360	0.000	0.004	0.996
Constant	0.650	0.067	0.000	0.708	0.066	0.000	0.370	0.041	0.000	1.311	0.199	0.000
Year_2015	0.027	0.008	0.001	0.506	0.058	0.000				0.314	0.046	0.000
Year_2016				0.556	0.072	0.000				0.177	0.036	0.000
Year_2017				0.438	0.091	0.000				0.166	0.019	0.000
Year_2018	-0.036	0.009	0.000	0.336	0.118	0.005				0.067	0.012	0.000
Year_2019	-0.088	0.008	0.000	0.155	0.151	0.305						
Year_2020				0.059	0.186	0.750						
Year_2021				-0.150	0.230	0.516						
D_Altitude_more_600	0.034	0.035	0.328				-0.101	0.046	0.026	-0.200	0.212	0.345
D_Field_crops_farms	0.092	0.021	0.000				0.090	0.013	0.000	0.069	0.029	0.016
AR(2)-test	-1.27		0.203	-1.63		0.104	1.48		0.140	-0.36		0.717
Hansen test	1186.88	Chi2(1156)	0.258	433.51	Chi2(437)	0.538	1193.22	Chi2(1138)	0.124	495.69	Chi2(467)	0.173
F-test	1078.04	F(40,1404)	0.000	607.84	F(42,460)	0.000	20.64	F(29,1483)	0.000	218.35	F(41,1410)	0.000
F-test: translog	25.51	F(29,1404)	0.000	15.54	F(29,460)	15.54	710.06	F(37,1483)		13.90	F(29,1410)	0.000
N. instruments	1197			480			1176			509		
N. groups	1405			461			1484			1411		

Source: own calculations

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